

The Organization of Turkic States within the Turkey– Kazakhstan–Uzbekistan Axis

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Abstract: The end of the Cold War and the dissolution of the Soviet Union affected the international order, changed all balances and created new geostrategic opportunities and threats. The dissolution of the Soviet Union added new dimensions to Turkey's relations with the Turkic States with which it shared common values, history, language and cultural ties. It created the opportunity for relations and cooperation to be maintained directly with independent states rather than under the Soviet roof. Turkey determined a Central Asian foreign policy line by evaluating social characteristics and historical associations. In this process, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan were at the top of the countries that Turkish foreign policy paid attention to. The relations that continued gradually with Kazakhstan could not make progress with Uzbekistan for many years. The main reason for this was determined as the isolationist and overprotective foreign policy experienced in Uzbekistan. However, the institutionalization of the Turkic Council in the following years enabled the expansion of relations between Turkic states. Indeed, Uzbekistan was also included in the relations that were advanced under the roof of the Turkic Council after 2009 in 2019. The organization, which took the name of the Organization of Turkic States in 2021, has assumed the role of a bridgehead in deepening relations. In the study, the Organization of Turkic States is examined on the axis of Turkey, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Explaining the contributions of the countries, the events in the global conjuncture and the stages achieved by the organization has been determined as the starting point of the study.

Keywords: Organization of Turkic States, Türkiye, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Central Asia

1. Introduction

The dissolution of the Soviet Union added new dimensions to Turkey's relations with states that share common values, history, language, and cultural ties. It created the opportunity for these relations and collaborations to be pursued not under the umbrella of the Soviet Union, but directly with independent states.

The radical changes in the international system, centered on the Central Asian region, directly affected Turkey and opened the way for Turkish foreign policy to take action. It was not possible for Turkey to remain indifferent to the independence of countries with which it shares common societal values. As the Turkish politicians of the period remarked, "this was a necessity, and history imposed certain responsibilities on Turkey."

Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, having gained independence as the largest states in the region, became a priority for Turkey. Turkey sought to expand channels of political cooperation with Central Asia. It regarded securing the support of Kazakhstan—possessing the region's largest economy and strongest influence—as particularly important. To this end, Turkey initially considered it appropriate to engage with Kazakhstan through joint platforms that would support political cooperation. It aimed to both prioritize Kazakhstan and simultaneously develop projects that would address the entire Central Asian region. Among the platforms where common policies could be pursued, the Turkic Summits undoubtedly stood out.

The parameters of Turkey's foreign policy toward Central Asia were identified as, first, a shared historical background, and second, the addition of political cooperation alongside economic partnership in the future. The strategy pursued appears to have been determined through a hybrid method. Accordingly, Turkey did not overlook either the social characteristics of the region or the grounds for commercial, financial, and political partnership provided by the era. In this context, shared historical and social values were instrumentalized in the name of present and future political and economic cooperation.

This study aims to explain the policies of Turkey, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan within the international political context of the establishment process of the Organization of Turkic States. It will outline the political stages through which the Organization has passed to reach its current position. The meetings held and decisions adopted by the Organization will be examined. Particular focus will be placed on the prominent roles of Turkey

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and Kazakhstan within the Organization of Turkic States. Furthermore, the importance of Uzbekistan's participation—albeit in the recent period—on a common platform with Turkey and Kazakhstan will be addressed.

The study will first present the period from the dissolution of the Soviet Union to the institutionalization of the Organization in 2009. The subsequent section will discuss the transition of the organization from the Turkic Council to the Organization of Turkic States. Ultimately, the analysis will explore the stages achieved by the Organization of Turkic States—from the conjuncture of the Soviet Union's collapse to its adaptation to the conditions of the changing global system—culminating in its consolidation of political power with Uzbekistan's accession.

2. From Its Establishment to 2009: The Turkic Council

The dissolution of the Soviet Union, which for many years had been perceived by Turkey as a source of security and ideological threat, and which constituted the main rationale behind Turkey's Western-oriented policies, brought not only regional advantages but also new responsibilities. Within Central Asia and the Caucasus, Turkey gained the opportunity to establish direct relations with independent states militarily and economically weaker than itself. Moreover, due to their shared language, religion, and culture, Turkey considered it possible to pursue common policies with them.

Turkey structured its relations with the countries of the region by taking into account international and regional dynamics. Accordingly, Turkey built its Central Asian policy upon the establishment of new mechanisms of economic and political cooperation that would reinforce its own role. However, the strategy to be pursued and the manner in which this foreign policy would gain functionality remained uncertain, as many critical developments unfolded during this period. Nevertheless, Turkey was able to take significant steps toward institutionalizing relations with these independent states with which it shared common values, thereby ensuring their continuity.

The Central Asian countries that gained independence, after the “economic and political dependence on Moscow” established by the Soviets, faced numerous challenges such as financial crises, ethnic tensions, and civil wars. In Kazakhstan, however, no major political problem was encountered thanks to the leadership of Nazarbayev (Olcott, 1993). By elevating national values in domestic politics, the process of nation-building was accelerated. Preventing ethnic conflict was made possible through political stability. In foreign policy, the leadership, endowed with diplomatic acumen, pursued an independent, peaceful, communicative, and secular bureaucracy.

Uzbekistan, governed under a presidential system, declared independence from the Soviet Union on 1 September 1991 (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2024a). The state, having initiated constitutional preparations, adopted its Constitution approximately one year later, on 8 December 1992. In the country's political system, which embraced the principle of separation of powers, the presidency was defined as holding broad authorities. In Uzbekistan's unitary state structure, the president stands at the head of the executive branch. Moreover, the president effectively controls both the judiciary and the legislature, while the parliament, in contrast, possesses only a weak political capacity of will (İrdem & Başak, 2023, p. 597).

Turkey sought to sustain political balance policies in the region in a stable manner and to maintain cooperation despite all challenges. In this context, the *Turkic Summits*, of which Kazakhstan was among the founding members, served as a political bridge between Ankara and the Turkic states. Through these summits, Turkey made it possible to establish long-term political connections with the countries of the region. In this way, Turkey aimed to render its policies in Central Asia more functional, with the expectation that Turkey's political sphere of influence would consequently expand.

The process of the Summits of the Turkic-Speaking Countries began following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, with the participation of countries sharing a common language—Azerbaijan in the South Caucasus, and Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan in Central Asia—together with Turkey. Initiated at

Turkey's initiative in 1992, this process has thus far witnessed ten "Summits of the Heads of State of Turkic-Speaking Countries" (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Foreign Affairs, n.d.b).

The first Turkic Summit, bringing together the heads of state of Kazakhstan, Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Kyrgyzstan, was held in Ankara in 1992. The then-president Turgut Özal and prime minister Süleyman Demirel anticipated that the summit would yield agreements in favor of economic and political cooperation. However, the outcomes of the summit fell short of expectations. The primary reason for this was the continuing economic, political, and demographic influence of Russia over Kazakhstan. In the post-independence period, the Russian population within Kazakhstan (Somuncuoğlu, 2016, p. 98) retained a significant weight for some time. Political elites in Moscow even demanded that Northern Kazakhstan be annexed to Russia. Nazarbayev, who later provided a permanent solution to this issue, relocated the country's capital from Almaty, situated near the eastern border, to Astana (Akmola), close to the northern border. During this process, Russian citizens occupying bureaucratic and military positions were not subjected to discrimination, and over time, part of the Russian population emigrated to Russia (Yalçinkaya, 2019).

Russia had concerns both economically and regarding the Russian ethnic community in Kazakhstan. To alleviate these concerns and prevent potential issues, Nazarbayev stated at the first summit that Kazakhstan would adhere to regional cooperation. It was emphasized that Kazakhstan did not intend to pursue ethnic or religious unity against Russia and that it was obliged to fulfill its responsibilities within the Commonwealth of Independent States, and thus toward Russia (Hale, 2003). Following the first summit, which entailed minimal obligations, the second summit was held in Istanbul in 1994. In subsequent summits, decisions were made to pursue cooperation in areas such as foreign affairs, culture, and education on realistic grounds, without causing discomfort to Russia. The meetings held in Bishkek in 1995 and in Tashkent in 1996 marked a shift from emotional unity toward expanding economic and cultural cooperation. Kazakhstan's participation and its balancing policies toward Russia helped prevent potential tensions in Astana–Moscow and Ankara–Moscow relations. The stances adopted in the following summits facilitated closer steps toward political unity (Sönmezoğlu, 2016).

The operational model of the summit was envisioned to resemble that of the Arab League or the Commonwealth of Nations. The exclusion of Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan from the summits demonstrated that Turkey's regional policy would primarily be pursued with countries receptive to political cooperation, particularly Kazakhstan (Aydın, 2021). In the 2000s, Turkey paid close attention to the *Turkic Council*, which had adopted this name and was envisioned as a platform for political unity in global politics. Kazakhstan's support for the summits and its inclusion of Turkey in the policies it pursued in the region were among the reasons why special attention was given to Astana.

Turkey sought to expand channels of political cooperation with Central Asia. It considered securing the support of Kazakhstan—the country with the region's largest economy and strongest influence—as particularly important. To this end, Turkey initially deemed it appropriate to engage with Kazakhstan through joint platforms that would support political cooperation. It aimed both to prioritize Kazakhstan and to develop projects that would address the entire Central Asian region. Among the platforms where common policies could be pursued, the Turkic Summits undoubtedly stood out. In addition, avenues targeting social life, such as education and culture, which could yield long-term positive outcomes, were also considered within this framework (Hiro, 2009). The long-term success of educational and cultural channels was expected to facilitate coordinated political steps based on the positive results achieved.

In addition, Turkey established the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA) in 1992 to institutionalize and sustain relations, as well as to develop cultural, economic, and other projects. In 1993, with contributions from Kazakhstan's Ministry of Culture, the *Turkic Council for Culture and Arts* (TÜRKSÖY) was founded. Through TÜRKSÖY, the use of the Latin alphabet in the region and the teaching of Turkish as spoken in Turkey were promoted (Sönmezoğlu, 2006, pp. 735–736). In line with this initiative, Kazakhstan gradually abandoned the Cyrillic alphabet and began using the Latin script in the 2000s.

Turkey made efforts to develop relations economically, politically, and culturally to support the independence of these countries. Policies were also pursued to help the republics establish integrated relations with the international system and the West. Within this process, Kazakhstan was prioritized on many local factors and

pursued a proactive policy in advancing relations. Positive feedback from Kazakhstan provided momentum to Turkish foreign policy, which was further reinforced by influences from the international system.

As the initial enthusiasm of the early years subsided, political relations with Kazakhstan in the 2000s acquired a more logical framework and were primarily conducted through the Turkic Summits. The summits held in 2001, 2006, and 2009 incrementally strengthened bilateral political relations, but it was only at the 2009 summit that these relations were elevated to a higher level. Factors such as ensuring Kazakhstan's economic suitability for international trade, the developments in local dynamics within Turkey, and the multifaceted policies of the Justice and Development Party (AK Party) enabled bilateral relations to reach the level of strategic partnership only by the end of the period.

At the 2001 Summit held in Turkey, the Istanbul Declaration was signed. Furthermore, in line with proposals by Nursultan Nazarbayev, the establishment of the *Council of Elders* and the *Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries* was suggested. The 2006 Summit, again held in Turkey after a 5.5-year interval, reiterated the same proposals. Policies based on integration were advanced further through Kazakhstan's positive responses to Turkey's minimal initiatives. Following the 2006 summit, which saw an increase in high-level reciprocal visits, Nazarbayev's friendly visit to Turkey on 30 September 2007 was particularly significant. In return, President Abdullah Gül visited Kazakhstan on 15 December 2007.

Diplomatic relations, which were initially launched very positively with Uzbekistan, became strained due to opposition views within Uzbekistan's domestic politics. Muhammad Salih, an Uzbek leader known for opposing the Karimov regime, was, however, labeled by Karimov and his administration as a terrorist attempting to overthrow the government. The presence of Muhammad Salih and his associates in Turkey in 1993 altered the appearance of Turkey-Uzbekistan relations. Karimov, disapproving of the opposition leader's presence in Turkey, pursued a policy that risked harming diplomatic relations with Turkey. Furthermore, he recalled Uzbek students studying in Turkey and, after 1998, decided that no students from Uzbekistan would be sent to Turkey, nor would Turkey accept any Uzbek students (Bekar, 2024, p. 367).

Islam Karimov made a total of four official visits to Turkey during his tenure, in 1991, 1994, 1995, and 1998 (Taldybaeva, 2021). During his 1994 visit, he reiterated his discomfort regarding Muhammad Salih's presence in Turkey. Although Turkey firmly stated that it would not permit Muhammad Salih to engage in political activities against Uzbekistan or the Karimov regime, the course of bilateral relations continued to be influenced by political unease over the Uzbek opposition figure's presence in Turkey (Bekar, 2024, p. 367). Despite the signing of the *Treaty of Eternal Friendship and Cooperation* between Turkey and Uzbekistan in 1996 (Taldybaeva, 2021) and Muhammad Salih's departure from Turkey, the two countries' relations failed to reach their expected diplomatic potential (Bekar, 2024, p. 367). Karimov also revoked visa-free travel to Turkey and closed schools through which Turkey maintained its soft power influence (Putz, 2022).

The Andijan Events in Uzbekistan in 2005 constituted another negative development that weakened Turkey-Uzbekistan relations. The Andijan Events encompassed incidents in the city of Andijan that were suppressed by law enforcement authorities. Protests erupted in response to the refusal to release businessmen who were reportedly unjustly detained, causing unrest throughout the country. According to Islam Karimov, the protests were carried out by radical Islamists attempting to overthrow the government. Turkey, disapproving of the excessive use of force by law enforcement, condemned Tashkent in coordination with the United Nations. This situation negatively affected Uzbekistan's political stance toward Turkey, and bilateral relations remained at a low level until Karimov's death in 2016 (Putz, 2022).

After the Turkic states gained independence, Turkey endeavored to support their continued sovereignty, emphasizing shared ancestry, language, religion, culture, and values. To integrate these states into the international community and provide the necessary investment and economic support, Turkey developed numerous projects in education, culture, politics, and economics. Simultaneously, policies were pursued to ensure that Turkish political influence could be effective in the region. In order to avoid isolation in the global system, the expansion of Ankara's political influence made it essential that every educational and cultural link established with Kazakhstan also reinforced common political platforms.

3. The Organization of Turkic States Following the Nakhchivan Agreement

The foundation for the year 2009, regarded as a milestone in the development of regional relations, was laid after 2007, during the first term of the AK Party government. The AK Party added new centers of influence alongside the Western mindset and interests, whose effects were felt more strongly during this period. The diversification of foreign policy preferences and the increased importance attributed to Central Asia provided momentum to political relations. At this point, it is necessary to note that developments in the international system, regional relations, and Turkish foreign policy prevented relations among Turkic states from being developed to the desired extent.

The United States requested support from neighboring Turkey for the northern front of the Iraq intervention. The issue, which emerged in Turkish domestic politics as the “1 March Motion,” initially generated significant diplomatic activity. Secondly, the widely held perception of the indispensability of Turkey’s strategic geopolitics was shaken. This outcome compelled Turkey to reaffirm the significance of its own geopolitical position. The tensions with the hegemonic power, the United States, placed Turkey in a difficult position in foreign policy, necessitating the demonstration of adherence to traditional Western-aligned policies and the restoration of diplomatic relations. Furthermore, Turkey’s influence in its region diminished, and regional policy objectives were not realized².

Another independent variable influencing Turkey’s regional policies was the expansion of the Shanghai Five into the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in 2001, following Uzbekistan’s accession. Initially established to resolve border issues inherited from China and the Soviet Union, the cooperation, once expanded into the SCO, committed its members to act jointly against extremism, terrorism, and separatism. In this context, the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure (RATS), the Interbank Consortium, and the Business Council were established within the SCO framework by the end of the 2000s (Arslan, 2019, p. 298). China’s close engagement with the region and the expansion of its cooperation signaled the challenges that would arise locally. Turkey’s already limited regional policies were further weakened under the influence of global powers. The effectiveness of policies and collaborations pursued by the United States, Russia, and China relegated Turkey to a secondary role in the political developments of the region.

Another political independent variable affecting Turkey’s regional policies was the wave of Color Revolutions that spread from Central Europe to the former Soviet space. These revolutions, which prompted Central Asian states to be particularly sensitive in their foreign relations, influenced Turkey’s policies in the region. Concerns arose that Turkey’s Western-oriented and democratic identity might generate distrust among Central Asian states. It became evident that the environment of trust in bilateral relations could quickly disintegrate and that these relations were inherently fragile. Turkey’s understanding approach toward the Kazakh administration, which was affected by the aftermath of the Color Revolutions, helped to strengthen the trust environment in political relations (Aydm, 2020, p. 474).

All these developments demonstrated the need to maintain relations and political unity on a more practicable platform, to enhance institutionalization, and to implement sustainable solutions. In this regard, by 2009, it is evident that Turkey’s policy toward Central Asia had deepened and was being pursued through rational steps. The initial enthusiasm of the 1990s and the period of disengagement after 2002 were replaced by years characterized by bilateral and multilateral cooperation. Turkey, geographically the easternmost European and the westernmost Asian country, structured its policies more realistically and on the basis of shared interests to move beyond a purely Western-oriented approach.

In the post-2009 period, it is appropriate to note that Turkey increasingly focused on Kazakhstan. Kazakhstan was identified as the most important partner in the developed Central Asia strategy. Relations with Kazakhstan were elevated to the level of strategic partnership, and the Turkic Summits were institutionalized as the Cooperation Council of Turkic Speaking States / Turkic Council.

² Most of the policies that Turkey symbolically represented as “red lines” in the region could not be implemented due to the U.S. intervention and the ensuing crisis. These included the protection of Turkmen populations, preventing Kirkuk from becoming a Kurdish-majority city, maintaining Iraq’s territorial integrity, and countering the PKK in the region, among others.

In 2009, political relations with Kazakhstan were deepened to a level unprecedented in previous periods, joint cooperation was expanded, and the Turkic Summits were given an international dimension. The institutionalization of the Turkic Summits as the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States / Turkic Council was made possible primarily through the active collaboration and coordination between Turkey and Kazakhstan. During this period, Turkey continued to regard Kazakhstan as the country closest to a “swing state” position in Central Asia. The policy articulated by Davutoğlu—“Turkey and Kazakhstan mutually lead the advancement and development of cooperation mechanisms among the Turkic republics”—highlights Kazakhstan’s privileged position in the Central Asian region (Yüce, 2016, p. 68).

Relations gained momentum in 2008 with the establishment of the Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries (TÜRKPA) in Istanbul. The agreement was signed by the Speakers of the Parliaments of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey. In 2009, TÜRKPA held its 1st General Assembly hosted by Azerbaijan, and it was decided that its secretariat would be permanently located in Baku (TÜRKPA, 2021). The establishment of TÜRKPA represented a significant form of cooperation bringing Turkey and Kazakhstan together in the new period. Being part of the same framework added a new dimension to bilateral relations.

The Turkic Council was established on 3 October 2009 through the Nakhchivan Agreement to promote comprehensive cooperation. Over the years, it has developed institutional links with organizations such as the *Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries* (TÜRKPA), founded in 2008, as well as the *International Turkic Academy*, the Turkic Business Council, the Turkic Culture and Heritage Foundation, and the International Organization of Turkic Culture (TÜRKSOY).

The *Nakhchivan Agreement on the Establishment of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States* was signed on 3 October 2009 during the 9th Summit held in Nakhchivan by Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan to institutionalize the ongoing process. The organization, referred to as the *Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States* or simply the *Turkic Council*, comprises the Council of Heads of State, the Council of Foreign Ministers, the Senior Officials Committee, the Council of Elders, and a Secretariat based in Istanbul (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (b), 2024).

In the preamble of the Nakhchivan Agreement, the member states reaffirmed their commitment to the purposes and principles of the United Nations Charter and defined the primary objective of the Organization as deepening comprehensive cooperation among Turkic states and contributing to regional and global peace and stability. The member states also expressed their adherence to fundamental principles such as democracy, respect for human rights, the rule of law, and good governance. Cooperation within the Organization is built upon a special solidarity derived from the shared history, culture, identity, and linguistic unity of Turkic-speaking peoples (Organization of Turkic States, 2024).

The Organization’s fundamental objectives and tasks, as set forth in Article 2 of the Nakhchivan Agreement, are as follows:

- Strengthening mutual trust among the parties;
- Preserving peace both within and beyond the region;
- Adopting common positions on foreign policy issues;
- Coordinating actions to combat international terrorism, separatism, extremism, and cross-border crime;
- Developing effective regional and bilateral cooperation in all areas of shared objectives;
- Creating favorable conditions for trade and investment;
- Promoting comprehensive and balanced economic growth, as well as social and cultural development;
- Discussing issues related to the rule of law, good governance, and the protection of human rights;
- Expanding interaction in the fields of science, technology, education, and culture;

- Encouraging interaction and more intensive communication through mass media;
- Promoting information exchange and judicial cooperation on legal matters (Organization of Turkic States, 2024).

The Council encourages cooperation in every possible area of common interest, including economic, military, technical, foreign policy, and cultural matters. Its core objectives are to establish effective regional and bilateral cooperation in all areas where mutual interests exist, including trade and economic relations, political and military affairs, education, transportation, environment, scientific and technical collaboration, credit and finance, energy, and culture. The Organization, which sets forth a strategic vision for inter-state unity, also aims to appropriately preserve, promote, and disseminate the cultural and historical heritage of Turkic peoples³.

The Turkic Council was established in 2009 as an international organization. Its official name is the *Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States*, commonly referred to as the Turkic Council, and it emerged through the institutionalization of the Turkic States' Heads of State Summits. The last of the Turkic Summits was held in 2010 in Istanbul.

The Turkic Council was officially launched during the 10th Turkic-Speaking Countries Summit held in Istanbul in September 2010. The Council's Secretariat⁴ is permanently based in Istanbul. This arrangement indicates that Turkey assumes a pivotal role in fostering political unity among Turkic Council members and that cooperative diplomacy will be conducted from Turkey as the central hub.

Turkey maintained its relations with Kazakhstan not in opposition to Russia, but in a manner that would not disturb Russian interests. The 2010 Turkic Council Summit exemplifies this approach. At the time, President Abdullah Gül emphasized that the Turkic Council meetings were not organized against any other country (specifically Russia), but served as a platform for cooperation and solidarity based on mutual equality. He particularly highlighted the development of economic cooperation (Efeğil, 2019, p. 167). This indicates that Turkey's diplomacy within the Turkic Council did not prioritize political unity as a goal, did not pursue interests contrary to Russia, and was primarily established to advance economic and commercial relations.

Education has been instrumentalized as a tool for Turkey's regional policy. The Turkic Council has provided an alternative means to achieve bilateral and regional unity in education. Accordingly, the 2012 Turkic Council meeting was convened under the theme of "Education, Science, and Cultural Cooperation" (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (c), 2024). The *Great Student Project*, initiated in 1992 for the Central Asian Turkic Republics, was expanded in 2012. The more advanced *Türkiye Scholarships* program was subsequently managed by the Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities (YTB). One of the most significant contributions under the education and science theme was reaching a consensus on the preparation of joint textbooks and curricula. Another key development was the decision to establish the *Union of Turkic Universities* and the Turkic Scientific Research Fund (TÜRKÜNİB, 2021).

Following the founding meeting in Istanbul, the first Turkic Council Summit was held on 20–21 October 2011 in Almaty under the theme of "Economic and Commercial Cooperation." The 2nd Turkic Council Summit took place on 22–23 August 2012 in Bishkek with the theme of "Education, Science, and Cultural Cooperation." The 3rd Summit was held on 15–16 August 2013 in Gabala, Azerbaijan, focusing on "Transportation." The 4th Summit was hosted by Turkey on 4–5 June 2014 in Bodrum under the theme of "Tourism." The 5th Summit took place on 11 September 2015 in Astana, with the theme of "Media and Information Technologies." The 6th Turkic Council Summit, held in Kyrgyzstan, centered on "Youth and Sports," during which Hungary participated as an observer member. The opening ceremony of the Turkic Council European Representation Office was held on 19 September 2019 in Budapest. At the 7th Summit, held on 15 October 2019 in Baku under the theme of "Supporting SMEs," Uzbekistan joined the Turkic Council as a full member (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (b), 2024).

³ For more detailed information, see: <https://www.turkkon.org/tr/turk-konseyi-hakkinda>

⁴ Turkey held the position of the Organization's first Secretary General until 2014, with former Ambassador Halil Akıncı serving in this role. Between 2014 and 2018, the Secretary General position was held by Ramil Hasan from Azerbaijan. Today, the Secretariat is based in Kazakhstan, with Ambassador Baghdad Amreyev currently serving as Secretary General.

Uzbekistan, which had previously refrained from joining regional organizations in line with its isolationist foreign policy, became a member of the Turkic Council—today known as the Organization of Turkic States—on 15 October 2019. As the country with the largest population in the region, Uzbekistan's accession significantly strengthened the Council geopolitically and provided a major political contribution to its Eurasian-oriented structure (Tanchum, 2022). It should be noted that Turkey played a decisive role in Uzbekistan's membership. During President Mirziyoyev's visit in 2017, Turkey invited Uzbekistan to join the Turkic Council and emphasized that the Council would be incomplete without Uzbekistan (Hasimova, 2019).

With Uzbekistan's accession, it became the second most populous country within the Turkic Council. Undoubtedly, several dynamics attracted Uzbekistan to the Council. Foremost among these was the fact that the Council was established in accordance with the principles of the United Nations. The principles of sovereign equality, territorial integrity and inviolability of borders, maintenance of international peace and law, security, and good-neighborly relations aligned closely with Uzbekistan's foreign policy principles (Hasimova, 2019).

Another factor in Uzbekistan's accession to the Turkic Council is that it provides a way to signal its significance as a key partner in regional cooperation. The changing foreign policy landscape requires Uzbekistan to secure a presence in both international and regional arenas. Through a reformist shift from isolationist policies toward a more open diplomacy, Uzbekistan appears to facilitate its regional ascent by joining international organizations. As the country with the largest population in the region, its economic potential can realistically be realized only through participation in regional and international cooperation.

The use of mass media is crucial for expanding and promoting areas of cultural unity. A key factor in facilitating interstate political cohesion is the establishment of strong bonds among citizens. In this context, TRT Avaz was launched on 21 March 2009, coinciding with the Nevruz Festival. In line with Ismail Gasprinski's motto, "Unity in language, thought, and work," the channel broadcasts programs on history, geography, culture, art, science, and education for Turkic-speaking populations. Serving as the common channel of the Turkic world, TRT Avaz collaborates intensively with the state channels of the Turkic Council member countries. Additionally, following a protocol signed in 2019, TÜRKSOY became a broadcasting sponsor. TRT Avaz is the only communication platform connecting the territories of Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and Tajikistan (TRT Avaz, 2024).

In 2019, Turkey launched the "Back to Asia" initiative to enhance its engagement and influence across the Turkic world and the entire Asian continent, as well as to strengthen its increasingly active Asia policies. Anticipating a shift in geopolitical developments and economic weight toward Asia, the initiative formulates comprehensive and holistic policies directed at the major powers and emerging countries of the 21st century within the continent. The *Back to Asia* initiative represents a long-term and systematic approach to Asia, taking into account not only the continent as a whole but also sub-regional and country-specific differences. Its objective is to strengthen comprehensive, multilateral, regional, and bilateral relations and cooperation with Asian countries. To achieve this, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs has established inter-agency coordination spanning the private sector, academia, civil society, and public institutions (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (d), 2021).

In 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Turkic Council held an "Extraordinary Video Conference Summit." The summit took place on 10 April 2020 with the aim of combating COVID-19 and enhancing intergovernmental coordination (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (c), 2024). Discussions focused on strengthening multilateral cooperation in health, maintaining economic and trade relations in the post-pandemic period, and ensuring uninterrupted transportation (Turkic Council, 2021). During this challenging period, fostering a sense of unity and renewing trust among member states strengthened Turkey's ties with all Central Asian countries (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (c), 2024).

On 12 November 2021, Turkey assumed the rotating chairmanship at the 8th Summit, held in Istanbul under the theme "Green Technologies and Smart Cities in the Digital Age." The summit, which coincided with the 30th anniversary of the independence of the Turkic states, marked the renaming of the organization as the "Organization of Turkic States (OTS)," with Turkmenistan joining as an observer member. During the summit,

the Turkic World 2040 Vision Document, outlining the medium- and long-term goals and functions of the OTS, was adopted (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (b), 2024).

The 9th Summit of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) was held on 11 November 2022 in Samarkand under the theme “A New Era for Turkic Civilization: Towards Common Development and Prosperity.” During this historic summit, the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus joined the OTS as an observer member. Following the earthquakes in Kahramanmaraş, an Extraordinary Summit of the OTS was convened in Ankara on 16 March 2023 under the theme “Disaster-Emergency Management and Humanitarian Aid” to demonstrate solidarity with Turkey. At the Ankara Summit, the long-negotiated Establishment Agreement of the Turkic Investment Fund was signed, and the Council of Heads of State decided to initiate the establishment of the *OTS Civil Protection Mechanism*. On 3 November 2023, the 10th Summit of the OTS was held in Astana, Kazakhstan, under the theme “TURKTIME,” where the Joint Declaration and Astana Charter were signed, 6 February was declared as the “Day of Commemoration and Solidarity for Disaster Victims,” and observer status in the ECO (Economic Cooperation Organization) was granted (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (b), 2024).

The holding of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) summit in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, demonstrated that Uzbekistan prefers a participatory foreign policy. The shared *Turkic World Vision – 2040* program reflects the determination of the Turkic states to jointly build a common future. The *Turkic World Vision – 2040* serves as a call for states to act collectively on the international stage. It prioritizes the enhancement of political coordination through joint action on global issues. Furthermore, it envisions the achievement of objectives such as trade integration, expansion of investment areas, harmonization of sectors, and the improvement of energy and transportation systems (Amreyev, 2022).

4. Conclusion

Over the decades following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the development of relations, shifts in focal points, and, of course, changes in the global system have facilitated improvements and advancements in certain aspects of the relations among Turkic states. However, for the same reasons, there were also periods during which these relations could not be significantly developed, became stagnant, or routine. Developments in Turkish foreign policy indicate that Turkey has sought to advance its relations with Kazakhstan and expand cooperation across various fields. As of 2009, it is evident that Turkey’s policy toward Central Asia had deepened and was being conducted through rational and systematic steps. The initial enthusiasm of the 1990s and the period of distancing after 2002 gave way to years characterized by bilateral and multilateral cooperation. Straddling the East and the West—being the most eastern of European countries and the most western of Asian ones—Turkey has sought to construct its policies on a more realistic and mutually beneficial basis, moving beyond a purely Western-centered approach.

The Turkish Summits, which had not achieved stability until 2009, were institutionalized as the Turkic Council. Efforts were made to establish cooperation and take joint steps in various fields such as education, economy, youth, culture, and sports. Kazakhstan’s significant contributions to the establishment of the Turkic Council facilitated the renewal of the leadership perception toward Kazakhstan, which constitutes an influential factor in Turkish foreign policy.

Strategically advancing relations between Turkey and Uzbekistan contributes to strengthening ties among Turkic states and building a shared future. The coexistence and potential realization of the largest Turkic nations are significant for all Turkic states. It becomes evident that Turkey evaluates the Central Asian region in both geostrategic and geoeconomic terms. Kazakhstan, as the largest and most influential country in the region, and Uzbekistan, following its accession to the Turkic Council, are considered priorities within the framework of the contributions they have provided and can provide to Turkish foreign policy.

%9Cİkeler,Kurucu%20belgesi%202011%20y%C4%B1%C4%B1nda%20imzalanm%C4%B1%C5%9Ft%C4%B1r

Republic of Turkey Ministry of Foreign Affairs (d). (2021). *Our Entrepreneurial and Humanitarian Foreign Policy on the Eve of 2021*. Booklet Prepared on the Occasion of the Submission of the 2021 Fiscal Year Budget Proposal of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the Grand National Assembly of Turkey.

Somuncuoğlu, A. (2016). Geographical Imaginations in Kazakhstan-Russia Relations. *Gazi Turkology*, 19(1), 95–121.

Sönmezoğlu, F. (2006). *Turkish Foreign Policy from World War II to the Present*. Istanbul: Der Publications.

Taldybaeva, D. (2021). The New Era of Turkey-Uzbekistan Relations. Akhmet Yassawi University, Eurasian Research Institute. <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/turkiye-ozbekistan-iliskilerinin-yeni-donemi/?lang=tr>

Tanchum, M. (2022, June 8). New Turkey-Uzbekistan Strategic Partnership Accelerates Turkey's Rise as a Eurasian Agenda-Setter. *The Turkey Analyst*. <https://www.turkeyanalyst.org/publications/turkey-analyst-articles/item/688-new-turkey-uzbekistan-strategic-partnership-accelerates-turkey%E2%80%99s-rise-as-a-eurasian-agenda-setter.html>

TRT Avaz. (2024). *About Us*. <https://www.trtavaz.com.tr/hakkimizda>

Turkic Council. (2021). *Turkic Council Leaders Gathered on 10 April 2020 for the Extraordinary Summit on the Coronavirus Pandemic*. https://turkkon.org/tr/haberler/turk-konseyi-liderleri-10-nisan-2020-tarihinde-koronavirussalgini-gundemiyle-duzenlenen-olaganustu-zirvede-bir-araya-geldiler_1991

TÜRKPA. (2024). *History of the Turkic Parliamentary Assembly*. https://turkpa.org/tr/content/about_turkpa/history

TÜRKÜNİB (Union of Turkish Universities). (2024). <http://turkunib.org/tr>

Yalçınkaya, A. (2019). *Political and Economic Structures and Foreign Policies of the Caucasus and Central Asian Countries*. In H. Kılıç & E. Toprak (Eds.), *Politics in Central Asia and the Caucasus*. Eskişehir: Anadolu University Press. E-ISBN: 978-975-06-3599-1.

Yüce, S. (2016). *The Role of Tourism in the Turkic World in Terms of International Relations (IR): A Social Constructivist Approach*. *Journal of International Turkic World Tourism Studies*, 1(1), 65-73.

William, H. (2003). *Turkish Foreign Policy 1774-2000*. Translated by P. Demir. İstanbul: Mozaik Publishing.